

CHALLENGES IN ENGLISH READING AMONG GRADE 7 STUDENTS AS BASIS FOR READING INTERVENTION PLAN

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the challenges in English reading among Grade 7 students at Lupigue Integrated School as basis for a reading intervention plan. Using a descriptive research design, the study involved 28 purposively selected Grade 7 students who did not pass the Phil-IRI group screening test for School Year 2024–2025. Data were analyzed through frequency and percentage, weighted mean, and analysis of variance. Findings revealed that most respondents were 13 years old, male, from poor to low-income households, and had parents with low educational attainment. In reading performance, students were generally at the instructional level in word recognition and reading speed, but most were at the frustration level in reading comprehension and vocabulary skills. Among learner-related challenges, reading comprehension and vocabulary skills emerged as the most serious concerns, while word recognition and reading speed were also challenging. For teacher-related challenges, feedback and reading resources were identified as major concerns, whereas teaching methods and communication style were not generally perceived as problematic. Significant differences were found in learner-related challenges when grouped according to age, sex, and parents' educational level, particularly in reading comprehension and reading speed. In teacher-related challenges, sex showed a significant difference only in teaching methods, while age, socio-economic status, and parents' educational level showed no significant differences. The study concludes that Grade 7 students need targeted reading support, especially in comprehension and vocabulary, and that a structured reading intervention plan is necessary to improve their overall English reading performance in school and support their academic growth across subjects.

Keywords: *English reading, reading comprehension, vocabulary skills, Grade 7 students, reading intervention plan*

INTRODUCTION

Reading is a foundational skill that serves as the basis for learning across subject areas. It enables students to understand, use, evaluate, and reflect on texts in ways that help them achieve academic goals and develop their knowledge and potential. Students with strong reading skills are better able to understand textbooks, solve word problems in mathematics, analyze literary works, and grasp scientific ideas. In addition, reading helps expand vocabulary, strengthen language abilities, and improve the way students express their thoughts in both written and oral communication (Mo, 2019; National Reading Panel, 2000).

Beyond academic success, reading also supports personal growth and lifelong learning. It exposes readers to different cultures, experiences, and perspectives, which can help develop empathy and a deeper understanding of others. Literacy is also recognized as a lifelong process that empowers individuals and supports fuller participation in society, while research has suggested that reading literary fiction may strengthen social understanding or theory of mind (Kidd & Castano, 2013; UNESCO, 2026).

However, despite its importance, many students continue to struggle with reading, especially in English. Research shows that difficulties in vocabulary knowledge and reading comprehension are common among linguistically diverse learners, particularly when they have limited opportunities for strong academic language support. When students do not receive enough structured reading and vocabulary instruction, they may find it hard to understand lessons, engage meaningfully with texts, and perform well in school. These challenges can affect both their confidence and their academic achievement (Lesaux et al., 2010; Lesaux et al., 2014).

Globally, the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) identifies substantial reading challenges among students. For instance, in the 2022 PISA results, countries like Singapore, Ireland, and Estonia consistently ranked at the top in reading proficiency, with Singapore leading the path. For example, Cambodia has a relatively high number of low-performing students, with about 92% failing to achieve basic competency. Similarly, the United States demonstrated that 20% of its students performed below the basic level, which was a notable improvement compared to many other OECD countries. Proficiency in reading directly impacts children's academic advancement, underscoring the global need for interventions.

Despite significant adjustments made after a poor performance in the 2018 Program for International Study Assessment results, the reading competency of Filipino students in 2022 remains a serious issue. Less than one-quarter of students met the minimum standards for reading, mathematics, and science competencies. The 2023 PISA results indicate that the Philippines continues to lag significantly behind the global average in all

crucial categories, although the country did show some improvement in ranking compared to 2018.

From the result of the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) conducted for Grade 7 students at Lupigue Integrated School, a significant challenge was identified in their reading comprehension levels. 30% of the students were classified under the "Instructional" level, indicating they can read with some guidance, while 50% of the students fell under the "Frustration" level. This means they struggle significantly with reading, particularly in comprehension, and are unable to independently grasp the content of the texts they encounter. This poses a challenge for the students at Lupigue Integrated School as it impairs their ability to absorb lessons, especially in subjects where reading comprehension is crucial for understanding the material.

These reading challenges not only hinder academic progress but also affect students' confidence and motivation to learn. Students who experience reading difficulties often report lower academic self-efficacy and tend to perform less successfully in school than their peers. When they struggle to read fluently, they may become frustrated, which can lead to disengagement from classroom learning. Over time, this pattern may widen the gap between struggling readers and more proficient readers, making it even harder for them to keep pace with lessons and comprehend written materials in English and other subjects that rely heavily on reading (Bergey et al., 2018; Retelsdorf et al., 2014; Stanovich, 1986).

Hence, it is important to conduct a study to address reading issues by creating a reading intervention plan for Grade 7 students. The intervention aims to improve their reading and comprehension skills, ultimately boosting their academic performance. This research is crucial as current reading programs may not effectively target the specific challenges faced by these students. The goal of this study is to bridge the gap and offer an effective reading intervention plan to help struggling readers.

Research Questions

This study aimed to identify the challenges encountered in reading of Grade 7 students as basis for a reading intervention plan. It sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - a. age
 - b. sex
 - c. socio-economic status
 - d. parent's educational level
2. What is the reading performance level of the Grade 7 students in terms of:
 - a. Word Recognition
 - b. Reading Speed
 - c. Reading Comprehension
 - d. Vocabulary Skills

3. What are the learner-related challenges encountered by the Grade 7 students in their English reading performance in terms of:
 - a. Word Recognition
 - b. Reading Speed
 - c. Reading Comprehension
 - d. Vocabulary Skills
4. What are the teacher-related challenges encountered by the Grade 7 students in reading English in terms of:
 - a. Teaching Methods
 - b. Feedback
 - c. Communication Style
 - d. Reading Resources
5. Is there a significant difference in the learner-related challenges encountered by the Grade 7 students in reading English when grouped according to profile?
6. Is there a significant difference in the teacher-related challenges encountered by the Grade 7 students in reading English when grouped according to profile?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized the Descriptive Research Design to identify the challenges encountered in reading by Grade 7 students as basis for a reading intervention plan. Descriptive Research design according to Sousa et al. (2017) describes variables and the relationships that naturally exist between and among them. Particularly, the descriptive research will be used since the present study aimed to describe the respondents' profile, learner-related and teacher-challenges encountered by the Grade 7 students in reading English. Hence, this is the most appropriate research design to achieve the main objective.

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted at Lupigue Integrated School located in Cabisera 10, City of Ilagan, Isabela, specifically in the Junior High School department. Lupigue Integrated School is a public institution that has been providing education since its establishment in 1963. The school serves students from elementary to senior high school and is situated in a rural area, catering to a diverse student population. Currently, the school has a total of 701 students, with 357 in elementary, 221 in junior high school, and 123 in senior high school.

Selection and Description of Respondents

The respondents of the study were Grade 7 students enrolled in School Year 2024–2025 at Lupigue Integrated School. Using purposive sampling, the researcher selected 28 out of the 56 Grade 7 students who did not pass the Phil-iRI group screening test –

each having scored below 28 out of 40 on the pre-test. 7 students who did not pass the Phil-IRI grouped screening test.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers sought permission from the Division Schools Superintendent of the Division of the City of Ilagan to conduct the present study through official channels. After permission was granted, the researcher personally administered the questionnaire to the respondents in coordination with the respective school head. The researcher ensured compliance with the Data Privacy Act regarding the respondents' profiles and questionnaire responses. Furthermore, the researcher distributed the questionnaire to the students for the learner-related challenges. For the teacher-related challenges, the advisers of the Grade 7 students were the ones who administered the survey. After completing the questionnaire, the researchers collected, analyzed, and interpreted the data.

Statistical Treatment of Data

After collecting the data, the researcher analyzed them using statistical tools, including frequency and percentage, weighted mean, and ANOVA.

Frequency and Percentage Count was used to determine the respondents' profiles and the level of the reading performance in English.

Weighted Mean was utilized to determine the learner-related and teacher-related challenges encountered by the Grade 7 students in reading English.

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was employed to ascertain significant differences in the learner-related and teacher-related challenges encountered by the Grade 7 students in reading English when grouped according to profile.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. **What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:**
 - a. Age

Table 1
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents as to Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
13 years old	20	71.43
14 years old	6	21.43
15 years old	0	0
16 years old	0	0
17 years old	2	7.14
Total	28	100

Table 1 displays the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents as to their age.

The data reveal that 20 or 73.43% of the respondents are 13 years old; 6 or 21.43% of them are 14 years old, and two or 7.14% of them are 17 years old. Most participants fall under the typical grade 7 age range of 13–14 years old, reflecting the normal progression of Grade 7 students without interruption. The two 17-year-old students are overage because their primary education was interrupted and are enrolled in the Alternative Learning System program.

The findings align with Belga et. al study on the Numeracy Level and Performance of Grade 7 students' in Mathematics, which provides data on the age distribution of Grade 7 students. The study found that out of 132 students, 62 (47.0%) were 13 years old, 36 (27.3%) were 12 years old, and 19 (14.4%) were 14 years old. This indicates that the majority of Grade 7 students in the study were 13 years old, supporting the finding that most participants in this grade level are typically 13 years old.

b. Sex

Table 2
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents as to Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	15	53.57
Female	13	46.43
Total	28	100

Table 2 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of their sex.

The data reveals that 15 or 53.57% of the respondents are **males and 13 or 46.43 % of them are females. It implies that the population in the study area is dominated by men.**

The findings of this study are similar to Piechura-Couture et al., (2013) indicating that schools tend to have a higher population of male students. There are more male students in barrio schools because there are simply more boy children living in the barangays near the school.

c. Socio-Economic Status

Table 3
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents as to Socio-Economic Status

Socio-Economic Status	Frequency	Percentage
Less than Php 10,957 per month	15	53.57
Between Php 10,957 and Php 21,914 per month	12	42.86
Between Php 21,914 and Php 43,828 per month	1	3.57
Between Php 43,828 and Php 76,669 per month	0	0
Between Php 76,669 and Php 131,484 per month	0	0
Between Php 131,484 and Php 219,140 per month	0	0
Php 219,140 and above per month	0	0
TOTAL	28	100

Table 3 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents as to socio-economic status.

The socio-economic classifications, as defined by the Philippine Institute for Development Studies (PIDS) (2022) in 2018, categorize households based on their monthly income. Those earning below ₱10,957 are classified as poor, while individuals with an income between ₱10,957 and ₱21,914 fall under the low-income but not poor category. The lower middle class consists of those earning ₱21,914 to ₱43,828, whereas the middle class earns between ₱43,828 and ₱76,669. The upper middle class has an income range of ₱76,669 to ₱131,484, while those earning between ₱131,484 and ₱219,140 are considered upper middle but not rich. Lastly, individuals with a monthly income of ₱219,140 and above are classified as rich. These classifications were based on data from the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA)

The data on the table show that an income of less than Php 10,957 per month has the frequency of 15 or 53.57%. This is followed by an income between Php 10,957 and Php 21,914 per month with 12 or 42.86%, while an income of between Php 21, 914 and Php 43, 828 per month has the lowest frequency of one or 3.57%. This means that most of the respondents belong to the poor to low income socio-economic status.

d. Parent's Educational Level

Table 4
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents as to Parent's Educational Level

Parental Education Level	Frequency	Percentage
Elementary Undergraduate	9	32.143
Elementary Graduate	7	25
High School Undergraduate	3	10.714
High School Graduate	3	10.714
College Undergraduate	4	14.286
College Graduate	2	7.143
With Master Units	0	0
Master's Degree Holder	0	0
With Doctorate Units	0	0
Doctorate Degree Holder	0	0
Total	28	100

Table 3 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of parental education level.

The data reveal that Elementary Undergraduate has the highest frequency of nine or 32.143% of the total population while College Graduate has the lowest frequency of two or 7.143%. Lastly, With Master Units, Master's Degree and Doctorate Degree have the zero or no percentage.

This means that most of the parents of the respondents are elementary undergraduate. It implies that most of them did not pursue higher education. Parents with low educational levels negatively affect their children's reading ability because they cannot assist with reading tasks at home, cannot monitor or follow up on their progress, and often lack the knowledge and resources needed to reinforce effective reading strategies.

The findings of this study align with Raza and Shah (2009) study, which found that a significant number of students come from families where parents have low educational attainment.

7. What is the level of the reading performance of the Grade 7 students?

a. Word Recognition

Table 5

The Reading Performance Level of the Grade 7 Students as to Word Recognition.

Word Recognition	Frequency	Percentage
Independent	0	0
Instructional	20	71.43
Frustration	8	28.57
TOTAL	28	100

Table 5 displays the reading performance level of the Grade 7 students as to word recognition.

The data reveal that 20 or 71.43 of the respondents are at the instructional level in word recognition; eight or 28.57% of them fall under the frustration level, and zero or none of the respondents are at the independent level. The data implies most of the respondents cannot recognize words independently so can they need assistance and benefit from guided reading instruction.

In an Informal Reading Inventory like the Phil-IRI, the independent level is defined by 98–100% word-recognition accuracy (texts a student can read entirely on their own), the instructional level by 90–97% accuracy (texts they can handle with guided support), and the frustration level by below 90% accuracy (texts too difficult even with assistance).

This is similar to the assessment conducted by Dela Rosa (2019), in which 159 Grade 7 students were evaluated on word recognition. The results showed that when using English texts, 25 students (approximately 15.7%) were at the instructional reading level, while for Filipino texts, 30 students (about 18.9%) were at the instructional level.

b. Reading Speed

Table 6

The Reading Performance Level of the Grade 7 Students as to Reading Speed

Speed Level	Frequency	Percentage
Independent	13	46.43
Instructional	11	39.29
Frustration	4	14.29
TOTAL	28	100

Table 6 shows the level of the reading performance of the respondents in terms of reading speed.

The data reveal that 13 or 46.43% are at the independent level in reading speed; 11 or 39.29% of them are at the instructional level, and four or 14.29% of them are at the frustration level.

The data imply that 13 respondents have adequate reading speed, but 11 respondents still require guidance, and four respondents struggle noticeably. One factor that contributed to their independent reading performance is the suitability and familiarity of the reading materials used. Since the texts are appropriate for their level, it allowed them to decode words quickly, maintain good pacing, and understand the material more easily.

To determine the reading speed of the students, the PHIL-IRI formula was used: $\text{Reading Speed} = (\text{Number of Words Read} \times 60) \div \text{Reading Time in Seconds}$. This formula measures how many words a student can read in one minute. In this study, a passage containing 364 words was used, and one of the students took 90 seconds to read it. Using the Phil-IRI formula, the computation was $(364 \times 60) \div 90 = 242.67$ words per minute, which determined the student's reading speed. Through this formula, the reading speed levels of students—whether independent, instructional, or frustration—can be accurately identified.

The study of Gedik and Akyol (2022) shows that reading speed continues to increase up to school-leaving age and starts to decline slowly around age 40, with a decrease of about 10% by age 70. This progression underscores the importance of developing reading speed during school years to support lifelong reading habits. Similarly, Sosial (2022) assessed the reading speed and comprehension of 200 students from sixth to ninth grades. The results indicates that reading speed increases with age, with ninth-grade students reading the fastest and seventh-grade students reading the slowest.

c. Reading Comprehension

Table 7
The Reading Performance Level of the Grade 7 Students as to Reading Comprehension

Reading Comprehension Level	Frequency	Percentage
Independent	0	0
Instructional	2	7.14
Frustration	26	92.86
TOTAL	28	100

Table 7 presents the reading performance level of the grade 7 students as to reading comprehension.

The data reveal that 26 or 92.86% of the respondents are at the frustration level in reading comprehension; two or 7.14% of the respondents are at the instructional level, and zero or none of them are at the independent level.

This implies that the majority of the respondents have difficulty in understanding what they read.

This is similar to the findings of Reyes (2020) which showed that approximately 85% of the respondents were categorized at the frustration level due to difficulties in identifying key ideas, understanding complex vocabulary, and making inferences. The study suggests that lack of prior knowledge and insufficient vocabulary were common barriers to comprehension, and that instructional support was necessary to improve reading comprehension.

d. Vocabulary Skills

Table 8
The Reading Performance Level of the Grade 7 Students as to Vocabulary Skills

Vocabulary Skills Level	Frequency	Percentage
Independent	0	0
Instructional	9	32.14
Frustration	19	67.86
Total	28	100

Table 8 shows the level of the reading performance of the respondents as to vocabulary skills.

The data reveal that 19 or 67.86% of the respondents are at the frustration level in vocabulary skills; 9 or 32.14% of them are at the instructional level, and zero or none fall under independent level. The data implies that most of the respondents have limited vocabulary knowledge, which can hinder their ability to understand texts, express ideas clearly, and engage effectively in academic discussions.

The findings align with the study by Garcia and Pagcaliwagan (2021), titled "Vocabulary Learning Plan for Grade-7 Learners in Bauan, Batangas," published in the International Journal of Recent Innovations in Academic Research. Their research highlights that a significant number of Grade 7 students in Bauan, Batangas struggle with vocabulary skills, often performing at frustration level.

3. What are the learner-related challenges encountered by the Grade 7 students in their English reading performance in terms of:

a. Word Recognition

Table 9
The Learner-related Challenges Encountered by the Grade Students in their English Reading Performance in terms of Word Recognition

Word Recognition	Average Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. I have a hard time knowing words in English. <i>(Nahihirapan akong kilalanin ang mga salitang Ingles.)</i>	2.54	Challenging
2. I guess words instead of sounding them out. <i>(Hinuhulaan ko ang mga salita kaysa binibigkas ang mga ito.)</i>	3.25	Very Challenging
3. I find it hard to read words that are spelled strangely. <i>(Hirap akong basahin ang mga salitang kakaiba ang baybay.)</i>	2.56	Challenging
4. I don't know many English words. <i>(Hindi ako bihasa o pamilyar sa maraming salitang Ingles.)</i>	2.54	Challenging
5. I have trouble saying new English words. <i>(Nahihirapan akong bigkasin ang mga bagong salitang Ingles.)</i>	2.56	Challenging
General Average Weighted Mean	2.69	Challenging

Table 9 presents the learner-related challenges encountered by the Grade 7 students in their English reading performance in terms of word recognition.

The data reveal that *I guess words instead of sounding them out* has highest weighted mean of 3.25 with a qualitative description of **Very Challenging**. Meanwhile, *I have trouble saying new English words, I have a hard time knowing words in English, I*

don't know many English words, and I find it hard to read words that are spelled strangely have lower weighted means of 2.56, 2.56, 2.54, and 2.54, respectively, all with a qualitative description of **Challenging**.

The findings indicate that the respondents find word recognition to be a challenge, ranging from challenging to very challenging.

This affirms the Dimapilis (2024) study which identified that many students relied on guessing words rather than decoding them, struggled with recognizing unfamiliar English words, and found it difficult to read words with irregular spelling patterns.

a. Reading Speed

Table 10
The Learner-related Challenges Encountered by the Grade 7 Students in their English Reading Performance in terms of Reading Speed

Reading Speed	Average Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. I read English very slowly. <i>(Mabagal akong magbasa sa Ingles.)</i>	2.54	Challenging
2. I can't read with the right feeling or tone. <i>(Hindi ko mabasa nang may tamang tono o damdamin.)</i>	3.11	Challenging
3. I lose focus and slow down when I read English. <i>(Nawawala ang aking pokus at bumabagal ako kapag nagbabasa ng Ingles.)</i>	3.13	Challenging
4. I feel bad when I read slower than my classmates. <i>(Nalulungkot ako kapag mabagal akong magbasa kaysa sa mga kaklase ko.)</i>	3.11	Challenging
5. I can't understand words fast when I read. <i>(Nahirapan akong intindihin agad ang mga salita kapag ako'y nagbabasa.)</i>	3.36	Very Challenging
General Average Weighted Mean	3.05	Challenging

Table 10 shows the learner-related challenges encountered by the Grade 7 students in their English reading performance in terms of reading speed.

The data reveal that I can't understand words fast when I read has the highest weighted mean of 3.36 with a qualitative description of **Very Challenging**. Meanwhile, *I lose focus and slow down when I read English, I can't read with the right feeling or tone, I feel bad when I read slower than my classmates, and I read English very slowly* have lower weighted means of 3.13, 3.11, 3.11, and 2.54, respectively, all with qualitative description of **Challenging**.

The findings indicate that the respondents find reading speed as a challenge, ranging from challenging to very challenging, in their English reading performance.

The findings affirm the study "Reading Performance of Grade 7 Students of Rosario National High School: Basis for Developing Reading Intervention Materials" by Medrano (2019) which revealed that a majority of the participants struggled with reading aspects such as pronunciation, syllabication, and speed rate.

b. Reading Comprehension

Table 11
The Learner-related Challenges Encountered by the Grade 7 Students in their English Reading Performance in terms of Reading Comprehension

Reading Comprehension	Average Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. I find it difficult to understand the main idea of what I read. <i>(Hirap akong maintindihan ang pangunahing ideya ng aking binasa.)</i>	3.64	Very Challenging
2. I can't tell the story again after I read it. <i>(Hindi ko kayang ikuwento muli ang nabasa ko.)</i>	3.50	Very Challenging
3. I can't guess what the text means. <i>(Hindi ko mahulaan ang kahulugan ng binabasa.)</i>	3.29	Very Challenging
4. I need to know things before I understand a new text. <i>(Kailangan muna akong matuto bago maintindihan ang bagong binabasa.)</i>	3.21	Challenging

5. I need my teacher or classmates to help me understand. <i>(Kailangan ko ang tulong mula sa guro o kaklase para maintindihan ang binabasa.)</i>	3.34	Very Challenging
General Average Weighted Mean	3.40	Very Challenging

Table 11 shows the learner-related challenges encountered by the Grade 7 students in their English reading performance in terms of reading comprehension.

The data reveal that *I find it difficult to understand the main idea of what I read, I can't tell the story again after I read it, I can't guess what the text means, and I need my teacher or classmates to help me understand* have higher weighted means of 3.64, 3.50, 3.29, and 3.24, respectively, all with qualitative description of Very Challenging. Meanwhile, *I need to know things before I understand a new text* has lower weighted mean of 3.21 and a qualitative description of Challenging.

The findings indicate that the respondents find reading comprehension as a challenge, ranging from challenging to very challenging.

The findings are similar to the study conducted by Dela Rosa (2019) at St. Paul which assessed the reading comprehension and vocabulary levels of Grade II pupils. The findings indicates that the majority of these pupils were at the frustration level in both reading comprehension and vocabulary skills. This low proficiency was correlated with their performance in English, suggesting that inadequate vocabulary knowledge hampers students' ability to understand texts and succeed academically.

c. Vocabulary Skills

Table 12
The Learner-Related Challenges Encountered by the Grade 7 Students in their English Reading Performance in terms of Vocabulary Skills

Vocabulary Skills	Average Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. I see words that I don't know. <i>(May mga salita akong nakikita na hindi ko alam.)</i>	3.68	Very Challenging
2. I find it hard to use new words. <i>(Nahihirapan akong gamitin ang mga bagong salita.)</i>	3.29	Very Challenging
3. I can't understand what I read because I know few words.	3.32	Very Challenging

(Mahirap intindihin ang binabasa dahil kakaunti ang alam kong salita.)		
4. I forget new words. (Nakakalimutan ko ang mga bagong salita.)	3.14	Challenging
5. I don't get enough chances to learn new words. (Kaunti lang ang pagkakataon ko na matuto ng bagong salita.)	3.26	Very Challenging
General Average Weighted Mean	3.34	Very Challenging

Table 12 shows the learner-related challenges encountered by the Grade 7 students in their English reading performance in terms of vocabulary skills.

The data reveal that *I see words that I don't know, I can't understand what I read because I know few words, I find it hard to use new words, and I don't get enough chances to learn new words* have higher weighted means of 3.68, 3.32, 3.29, and 3.26, respectively, all with qualitative description of **Very Challenging**. Meanwhile, *I forget new words* has lower weighted mean of 3.14 and a qualitative description of **Challenging**.

The findings indicate that the respondents find vocabulary skills as a challenge, ranging from challenging to very challenging.

This is similar to the study of Rosyada and Apoko (2023) who conducted a study on lower secondary school students and found that many encountered difficulties in vocabulary learning, particularly in pronunciation, spelling, understanding word meanings, and retention. These challenges align with the high mean scores observed in statements related to encountering unknown words and struggling with comprehension due to limited vocabulary.

Table 13
Summary of the Learner-related Challenges Encountered by the Respondents in their English Reading Performance

Learner-Related Challenges	Average Mean Value	Interpretation
1. Word Recognition	2.69	Challenging
2. Reading Speed	3.05	Challenging
3. Reading Comprehension	3.40	Very Challenging
4. Vocabulary Skills	3.34	Very Challenging
Total Average Mean Value	3.12	Challenging

Table 13 shows the summary of the learner-related challenges encountered by the respondents in their English Reading Performance.

Among the learner-related challenges, reading comprehension has the highest average mean value of 3.40 with a qualitative description of **Very Challenging**. This is followed closely by vocabulary skills with an average mean value of 3.34 with a qualitative description of **Very Challenging**. Reading speed follows with an average mean value of 3.05 with a qualitative description of **Challenging**. This is followed by word recognition with an average mean value of 2.69 with a qualitative description of **Challenging**.

The results imply that reading comprehension and vocabulary skills are the most challenging for students because they require higher-order thinking and a strong language foundation. Since comprehension heavily relies on vocabulary knowledge, students who encounter unfamiliar words may struggle to make sense of the text, making these two skills the most significant barriers to effective reading performance.

The learner-related challenges of word recognition, reading speed, vocabulary skills, and reading comprehension are interconnected because difficulty in one area directly affects the ability to comprehend and read fluently. These challenges are considered learner-related because they stem from the individual student's cognitive abilities and skills, which determine their overall reading performance.

4. What are the teacher-related challenges encountered by the Grade 7 students in reading English.

a. Teaching Methods

Table 14
Teacher-related Challenges Encountered by the Grade 7 Students in Reading English in terms of Teaching Methods

Teaching Methods	Average Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. My English teacher does not explain much during class. <i>(Ang guro sa Ingles ay hindi masyadong nagpapaliwanag.)</i>	1.54	Strongly Disagree
2. My teacher uses traditional ways of teaching instead of new ways. <i>(Pakiramdam ko, mga lumang pamamaraan ng pagtuturo ang gamit ng aking guro sa halip na makabagong paraan.)</i>	1.29	Strongly Disagree
3. My teacher sometimes speaks Filipino instead of English. <i>(Napapansin ko na minsan ang aking guro ay nagsasalita sa Filipino imbes na Ingles.)</i>	1.79	Disagree

4. My teacher often translates English into Filipino instead of helping me understand the English words. <i>(Kadalasan, isinasalin sa Filipino ng aking guro ang Ingles sa halip na tulungan kaming maunawaan ang mga salitang Ingles.)</i>	2.56	Agree
5. My English teacher does not explain clearly during class. <i>(Para sa akin, hindi malinaw ang paliwanag ng aking guro sa Ingles sa panahon ng talakayan.)</i>	1.57	Strongly Disagree
General Average Weighted Mean	1.75	Disagree

Table 14 shows the teacher-related challenges encountered by the Grade 7 students in reading English in terms of teaching methods.

The data reveal that *My teacher often translates English into Filipino instead of helping me understand the English words* has the highest weighted mean of 2.56 with a qualitative description of **Agree**. On the other hand, *My teacher sometimes speaks Filipino instead of English* has a mean of 1.79 with a qualitative description of **Disagree**. Meanwhile, *My English teacher does not explain clearly during class*, *My English teacher does not explain much during class*, and *My teacher uses traditional ways of teaching instead of new ways* have lower weighted means of 1.57, 1.54, 1.29, and 1.57, respectively, all with qualitative description of **Strongly Disagree**.

The data reveal that the respondents do not agree that teaching methods is not a challenge in their English reading performance except the instance that teacher sometimes speaks Filipino instead of English which means that the language of instruction is perceived as a factor affecting their reading challenges. This suggests that difficulties in reading English may be more related to medium of instruction rather than the teaching methods.

The findings affirm the study by Chairunnisya et al. (2025) which explored students' views on various teaching strategies. The findings suggested that while students had preferences for certain strategies like brainstorming and predicting, they did not identify teaching methods as a primary obstacle in their reading performance.

b. Feedback

Table 15
Teacher-related Challenges Encountered by the Grade 7 Students in Reading English in terms of Feedback.

Feedback	Average Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. I get feedback about my reading mostly at the end of class. <i>(Madalas akong nakakatanggap ng feedback o punas tungkol sa aking pagbabasa pagkatapos ng klase.)</i>	3.96	Strongly Agree
2. My teacher asks questions only about facts and understanding. <i>(Ang mga tanong ng aking guro ay tungkol lamang sa mga katotohanan at pag-unawa.)</i>	3.18	Agree
3. The feedback my teacher gives is not clear and does not help me improve. <i>(Ang feedback o mga punang ibinibigay ng aking guro ay hindi malinaw at hindi nakatutulong sa aking pagpapabuti.)</i>	3.04	Agree
4. I wish my teacher gave me more detailed feedback on how to get better at reading. <i>(Nais ko sanang magbigay ng detalyadong feedback ang aking guro kung paano mapapabuti ang aking pagbabasa.)</i>	3.79	Strongly Agree
5. My teacher does not talk to my parents about how I am doing in reading. <i>(Hindi nakikipag-ugnayan and aking guro sa aking mga magulang tungkol sa aking progreso sa pagbabasa.)</i>	2.48	Disagree
General Average Weighted Mean	3.33	Strongly Agree

Table 15 displays the teacher-related challenges encountered by the Grade 7 students in reading English in terms of feedback.

The data reveal that *I get feedback about my reading mostly at the end of class* and *I wish my teacher gave me more detailed feedback on how to get better at reading* have the highest weighted means of 3.96 and 3.79 with a qualitative description of **Strongly Agree**. *My teacher asks questions only about facts and understanding* and *The feedback my teacher gives is not clear and does not help me improve* have means of 3.18 and 3.04 with a qualitative description of **Agree**. Meanwhile, *My teacher does not talk to my parents about how I am doing in reading* has the lowest weighted mean of 2.48 with a qualitative description of **Disagree**.

The results imply that the respondents agree to strongly agree that feedback is a challenge in their English reading performance. However, *My Teacher does not talk to my parents about how I am doing in reading* has the lowest weighted mean of 2.48, which means that parental communication is not seen as a significant issue compared to the need for more detailed and timely feedback from the teacher.

The findings affirm the study of Vattøy and Kari (2019) that students often find teacher feedback to be a challenge in their English reading performance, particularly when the feedback lacks clarity, is not timely, or does not effectively involve students in the learning process.

c. Communication Style

Table 16
Teacher-related Challenges Encountered by the Grade 7 Students in Reading English in terms of Communication Style

Communication Style	Average Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. My teacher judges my work without telling me how to improve. <i>(Hinuhusgahan ng aking guro ang aking mga gawa at hindi nagsasabi kung paano ako magbabago.)</i>	1.37	Strongly Disagree
2. I find it hard to ask my teacher questions about reading homework. <i>(Nahihirapan akong magtanong sa aking guro tungkol sa mga takdang-aralin sa pagbabasa.)</i>	1.89	Strongly Disagree
3. I feel uncomfortable because my teacher talks very seriously. <i>(Hindi ako komportable dahil ang aking guro ay laging seryoso sa pakikipag-usap.)</i>	1.07	Strongly Disagree
4. I find my teacher more approachable when I struggle with reading. <i>(Mas madaling lapitan ang guro ko kapag nahihirapan akong magbasa.)</i>	2.33	Disagree
5. My teacher uses words I do not understand. <i>(Ang aking guro ay gumagamit ng mga salitang mahirap maintindihan.)</i>	2.14	Disagree
General Average Weighted Mean	1.51	Strongly Disagree

Table 16 displays the teacher-related challenges encountered by the Grade 7 students in reading English in terms of communication style.

The data reveal that *I find my teacher more approachable when I struggle with reading, My teacher uses words I do not understand and My teacher uses words I do not understand* have higher weighted means of 2.33, and 2.14, respectively, with a qualitative description of **Disagree**. Meanwhile, *My teacher judges my work without telling me how to improve, I find it hard to ask my teacher questions about reading homework, My teacher uses words I don't understand, and I feel uncomfortable because my teacher talks very seriously* have low weighted means of 1.37 and 1.89, and 1.07 respectively, with a qualitative description of **Strongly Disagree**.

The results imply that the respondents do not find communication style as a challenge, ranging from disagree to strongly agree in their English reading performance.

The findings negate the study by Meriza Putri and Elmiati (2017), who found that students perceive communication style as a challenge in their learning experience. Meriza Putri and Elmiati's study revealed that students who viewed their teachers as highly versatile and responsive reported lower fears about communicating in class.

d. Reading Resources

Table 17
Teacher-related Challenges Encountered by the Grade 7 Students in Reading English in terms of Reading Resources

Reading Resources	Average Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. The reading materials my teacher gives are old or boring. <i>(Ang mga babsahing materyales na ibinibigay ng aking guro ay luma at nakakabagot.)</i>	3.20	Agree
2. My teacher uses notes and books a lot for reading practice. <i>(Ang aking guro ay madalas umamit ng mga tala at libro para sa pagsasanay sa pagbasa.)</i>	3.14	Agree
3. My teacher does not use different types of reading materials. <i>(Ang aking guro ay hindi gumagamit ng iba't ibang uri ng babasahing material.)</i>	2.32	Disagree

4. I find it hard to understand the reading materials because they do not relate to my life. <i>(Nahihirapan akong intindihin ang mga materyales na binabasa dahil hindi ito tumutugma sa aking karanasan.)</i>	3.93	Strongly Agree
5. My teacher does not encourage me to use other resources (like websites) to help me read better. <i>(Hindi ako hinihikayat ng aking guro na gumamit ng ibang material tulad ng websites at iba pang mga sanggunian para matulungan akong mapabuti ang aking pagbabasa.)</i>	2.56	Agree
General Average Weighted Mean	2.85	Agree

Table 16 displays the teacher-related challenges encountered by the Grade 7 students in reading English in terms of communication style.

The data reveal that *I find it hard to understand the reading materials because they do not relate to my life* has the highest weighted mean of 3.93 with a qualitative description of **Strongly Agree**. *The reading materials my teacher gives are old or boring, My teacher uses notes and books a lot for reading practice, My teacher does not encourage me to use other resources (like websites) to help me read better* have weighted means of 3.20, 3.14, and 2.56, respectively, all with qualitative description of **Agree**. Meanwhile, *My teacher does not use different types of reading materials* has the lowest weighted mean of 2.32 with a qualitative description of **Disagree**.

The results imply that the respondents agree to strongly agree that teaching resources is a challenge in their English reading performance. It suggests that while students perceive challenges with the relevance and engagement of reading materials, they still acknowledge that their teacher makes an effort to provide some variety. Hence, the issue may not be a complete lack of diverse reading resources but rather a mismatch between the materials used and the students' interests, experiences, or learning preferences.

This affirms the study by Linde and Daniela (2025) focusing on lower secondary schools in Rwanda which found a positive correlation between the use of English reading materials and students' language performance. The research emphasized that access to a variety of high-quality reading materials is essential for fostering reading proficiency.

Table 18
Summary of Teacher-Related Challenges Encountered by Students in their English Reading Performance

Teacher-Related Challenges	Average Mean	Interpretation
1. Teaching Methods	1.75	Disagree

2. Feedback	3.33	Strongly Agree
3. Communication Style	1.51	Disagree
4. Reading Resources	2.85	Agree
Total Average Mean Value	3.03	Agree

Table 18 shows the summary of the learner-related challenges encountered by the respondents in their English reading performance.

Among the challenges, Feedback has the highest mean value of 3.33 with a qualitative description of **Strongly Agree**. This is followed by Reading resources with an average mean value of 2.85 with a qualitative description of **Agree**. Teaching methods follow with an average mean value of 1.75 with a qualitative description of Disagree. Communication style has the lowest average mean value of 1.51 with a qualitative description of **Disagree**.

Feedback and Reading Resources are the most challenging teacher-related factors in students' English reading performance, as unclear guidance and outdated or unengaging materials hinder students' reading progress. In contrast, Communication Style and Teaching Methods are perceived as less challenging, suggesting that students generally find their teachers' instructions clear and their methods effective in supporting reading activities.

5. Is there a significant difference in the learner-related challenges encountered by the Grade 7 students in reading English when grouped according to their profile?

a. Age

Table 19
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Learner-Related Challenges encountered by the Grade 7 students in reading English when grouped according to Age

Students' Age and the following Learner Related Challenges Encountered in Reading English	Mean			P-value	Analysis	Remarks
	Age 13	Age 14	Age 17			
Word Recognition	2.62	2.87	2.80	0.605	p>0.05	Not Significant
Reading Speed	3.17	2.67	3.10	0.197	p>0.05	Not Significant
Reading Comprehension	3.47	3.07	3.70	0.034	p<0.05	Significant
Vocabulary Skills	3.42	3.12	3.20	0.447	p>0.05	Not Significant

Table 19 presents the results of the test of significant difference in the learner-related challenges encountered by the Grade 7 students in reading English when grouped according to age.

The results show that the p-value 0.034 for reading comprehension is less than the significance level of 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, there is a significant difference in the learner-related challenges in reading comprehension encountered by the Grade 7 students when grouped by age. This implies that the students aged 13, 14, and 17 differ in the challenges they encounter in English reading comprehension. It further inferred that students aged 13 experienced more challenges in reading comprehension as their mean score is higher than ages 14 and 17.

However, there is no significant difference in the learner-related challenges in word recognition, reading speed, and vocabulary skills encountered by Grade 7 students when grouped by age. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted at the 0.05 significance level. This finding confirms that the students do not differ in the challenges encountered in word recognition, reading speed, and vocabulary skills when grouped by age. It further indicates that students aged 13, 14, and 17 exhibit similar challenges in these areas.

The result is similar to the findings of Kolić-Vehovec et al. (2011), who found that metacognitive skills—critical for reading comprehension—develop significantly with age, showing that older students are better at monitoring and understanding texts than their younger peers.

b. Sex

Table 20
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Learner-Related Challenges encountered by the Grade 7 students in reading English when grouped according to Sex

Students' Sex and the following Learner Related Challenges Encountered in Reading English	Mean		P-value	Analysis	Remarks
	M	F			
Word Recognition	2.76	2.60	0.274	p>0.05	Not Significant
Reading Speed	3.33	2.73	0.004	p<0.05	Significant
Reading Comprehension	3.33	3.48	0.294	p>0.05	Not Significant
Vocabulary Skills	3.44	3.22	0.387	p>0.05	Not Significant

Table 20 presents the results of the test of significant difference in the learner-related challenges encountered by the Grade 7 students in reading English when grouped according to sex.

The results showed that the p-value 0.004 for reading speed is less than the significance level of 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance, thus, there is a significant difference in the learner-related challenges on reading speed encountered by the Grade 7 students when grouped by sex. This implies that male and female students differ in the challenges they encounter in English reading speed. It further inferred that female students experienced more challenges in reading speed as their mean score is higher than that the other group.

However, there is no significant difference in the learner- related challenges in word recognition, reading comprehension, and vocabulary skills encountered by Grade 7 students when grouped by sex. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted at the 0.05 significance level. This finding confirms that the students do not differ in the challenges encountered in word recognition, reading comprehension, and vocabulary skills when grouped by sex. It further indicates that male and female students exhibit similar challenges in these areas.

This is similar to the study of Keith and Reynolds (2008), which showed that females tend to process information faster than males during childhood and adolescence, including tasks related to reading and fluency, supporting the findings that female students experience more challenges in reading speed due to higher expectations for pace and performance.

c. Socio-economic Status

Table 21
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Learner-Related Challenges encountered by the Grade 7 students in reading English when grouped according to Socio-economic Status

Students' Socio - Economic Status and the following Learner Related Challenges Encountered in Reading English	Mean			P-Value	Analysis	Remarks
	Less than Php 12,082 per month	Between Php 12,082 and Php 24,164 per month	Between Php 24,164 and Php 48,328 per month			
Word Recognition	2.67	2.68	2.30	p>0.671	0.05	Not Significant
Reading Speed	2.99	3.12	3.20	p>0.803	0.05	Not Significant
Reading Comprehension	3.47	3.35	3.20	p>0.537	0.05	Not Significant
Vocabulary Skills	3.15	3.58	3.40	p>0.158	0.05	Not Significant

Table 22 presents the results of the test of significant difference in the learner-related challenges encountered by the Grade 7 students in reading English when grouped according to Socio-economic Status

The results show that the values for word recognition, reading speed, reading comprehension, and vocabulary skills are greater than the significance level of 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted at the 0.05 level of significance, thus, there is no significant difference in the learner-related challenges in word recognition, reading speed, reading comprehension, and vocabulary skills encountered by Grade 7 students when grouped by their socio-economic status.

This implies that the students do not differ in the challenges encountered in word recognition, reading speed, reading comprehension, and vocabulary skills when grouped by socio-economic status. It further indicates that students with similar socio-economic status exhibit similar challenges in these areas.

The results align with the study of Ofuani & Gbenedio (2018), which found no significant effect of socio-economic status on students' reading comprehension, suggesting that when educational support and resources are consistently provided, socio-economic differences do not necessarily lead to disparities in reading performance.

d. Parent's Educational Level

Table 22
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Learner-Related Challenges encountered by the Grade 7 students in reading English when grouped according to Parent's Educational Level

Students', Parents' Educational Level and the following Learner Related Challenges Encountered in Reading English	Mean						P-value	Analysis	Remarks
	Elementary Undergraduate	Elementary Graduate	High School Undergraduate	High School Graduate	College Undergraduate	College Graduate			

Word Recognition	2.74	2.69	2.68	2.70	2.77	2.30	p>0.98	p>0.05	Not Significant
Reading Speed	3.13	3.31	2.23	2.87	3.40	3.20	p>0.05	P=0.05	Significant
Reading Comprehension	3.49	3.31	3.50	3.33	3.40	3.20	p>0.854	p>0.05	Not Significant
Vocabulary Skills	3.43	3.29	3.15	3.40	3.33	3.40	p>0.977	p>0.05	Not Significant

Table 21 presents the results of the test of significant difference in the learner-related challenges encountered by the Grade 7 students in reading English when grouped according to parent's educational level.

The results showed that the p-value 0.05 for reading speed is equal to the significance level of 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at the 0.05 level of significance, thus, there is a significant difference in the learner-related challenges in reading speed encountered by Grade 7 students when grouped by their parents' educational level. This implies that the parents' educational levels differ in terms of the challenges their children encounter in English reading speed. It further indicates that students whose parents are college undergraduates experienced more challenges in reading speed as their mean score is higher than that of the other groups.

However, there is no significant difference in the learner-related challenges in word recognition, reading comprehension, and vocabulary skills encountered by Grade 7 students when grouped by parents' educational level. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted at the 0.05 significance level. This finding confirms that the students do not differ in the challenges encountered in word recognition, reading comprehension, and vocabulary skills when grouped by parents' educational level. It further indicates that students with similar parents' educational level exhibit similar challenges in these areas.

The study is the same with the findings of Hindman and Morrison (2010), who found that parental educational level significantly influences children's reading development, particularly in areas such as reading fluency and speed, due to the literacy-rich environments and support more educated parents typically provide.

6. Is there a significant difference in the teacher- related challenges encountered by the Grade 7 students in English reading when grouped according to their profile?

a. Age

Table 23
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Teacher-Related Challenges encountered by the Grade 7 students in reading English when grouped according to Age

Students' Age and the following Teacher-Related Challenges Encountered in English Reading	Mean			P-value	Analysis	Remarks
	Age 13 years old	Age 14 years old	Age 17 years old			
Teaching Methods	1.71	1.90	1.70	0.414	0.05	Not Significant
Feedback	3.24	3.50	3.70	0.295	0.05	Not Significant
Communication	1.47	1.63	1.60	0.283	0.05	Not Significant
Reading Resources	2.95	3.33	2.90	0.142	0.05	Not Significant

Table 23 presents the results of the test of significant difference in the teacher-related challenges encountered by the Grade 7 students in English reading when grouped according to age.

The results showed that the values for teaching methods, feedback, communication, and reading resources are greater than the significance level of 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted at the 0.05 level of significance, thus, there is no significant difference in the teacher-related challenges in teaching methods, feedback, communication, and reading resources encountered by Grade 7 students when grouped by age. This implies that the students do not differ in the challenges encountered in teaching methods, feedback, communication, and reading resources when grouped by age. It further indicates that students aged 13, 14, and 17 exhibit similar challenges in these areas.

This finding is supported by Brandmo and Gamlem's (2025) systematic review, which found that students aged 10–16 showed consistently similar perceptions of teacher-related factors—such as teaching methods, communication style, and feedback—indicating these do not vary significantly with age in lower secondary settings.

b. Sex

Table 24
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Teacher-Related Challenges encountered by the Grade 7 students in reading English when grouped according to Sex

Students' Sex and the following Teacher Related Challenges Encountered in Reading English	Mean		P-Value	Analysis	Remarks
	Male	Female			
Teaching Methods	1.60	1.92	$p < 0.010$	0.05	Significant
Feedback	3.35	3.31	$p > 0.751$	0.05	Not Significant
Communication	1.51	1.52	$p > 0.892$	0.05	Not Significant
Reading Resources	3.07	2.98	$p > 0.525$	0.05	Not Significant

Table 24 presents the results of the test of significant difference in the teacher-related challenges encountered by the Grade 7 students in English reading when grouped according to sex.

The results show that the p-value (0.01) for teaching methods is less than the significance level of 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis are rejected at the 0.05 level of significance, thus, there is a significant difference in the teacher-related challenges in teaching methods encountered by Grade 7 students when grouped by sex. This implies that male and female students differ in the challenges they encounter in teaching methods. It further infer that female students experienced more challenges in teachers' teaching methods as their mean score is higher than that the male group.

The findings are similar to Ruffing et al. which found that female students often exhibit a more detail-oriented cognitive style compared to male students. The study indicates that females tend to focus on details, process information more thoroughly, and are more meticulous in their approach to tasks, which may lead to them experiencing greater challenges with teaching methods that require specific attention to details or step-by-step procedures.

However, there is no significant difference in the teacher- related challenges in feedback, communication, and reading resources encountered by Grade 7 students when grouped by sex. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted at the 0.05 significance level. This finding confirms that the students do not differ in the challenges encountered in feedback,

communication, and reading resources when grouped by sex. It further indicates that male and female students exhibit similar challenges in these areas.

c. Socio Economic Status

Table 25
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Teacher-Related Challenges encountered by the Grade 7 students in reading English when grouped according to Socio Economic Status

Students' Socio-Economic Status and the following Teacher Related Challenges Encountered in Reading English	Mean			P-value	Analysis	Remarks
	Less than 12,082 per month	Between 12,082 and 24,164 per month	Between 24,164 and 48,328 per month			
Teaching Methods	1.79	1.75	1.50	p>0.300	p>0.05	Not Significant
Feedback	3.24	3.33	4.00	p>0.159	p>0.05	Not Significant
Communication	1.53	1.49	1.50	p>0.901	p>0.05	Not Significant
Reading Resources	2.97	3.02	3.50	p>0.338	p>0.05	Not Significant

Table 26 presents the results of the test of significant difference in the teacher-related challenges encountered by the Grade 7 students in reading English when grouped according to Socio Economic Status.

The results showed that the p-values for teaching methods, feedback, communication, and reading resources is greater than the significance level of 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted at the 0.05 level of significance, thus, there is no significant difference in the teacher-related challenges in teaching methods, feedback, communication, and reading resources encountered by Grade 7 students when grouped by their socio-economic status. This implies that students do not differ in the challenges encountered in teaching methods, feedback, communication, and reading resources when grouped by socio-economic status. It further indicates that students with similar socio-economic status exhibit similar challenges in these areas.

This finding supports the results of Korpershoek et al., who found no significant differences in student-reported teacher–student relationship quality across varying levels of socio-economic status, indicating that perceptions of teacher-related support—such as teaching methods, feedback, communication, and reading resources—tend to remain consistent regardless of students' SES background.

d. Parent's Educational Level

Table 26
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Learner-Related Challenges encountered by the Grade 7 students in reading English when grouped according to Parent's Educational Level

Students' Parents' Educational Level and the following Teacher Related Challenges Encountered in Reading English	Mean						P-Value	Analysis	Remarks
	Elementary Undergraduate	Elementary Graduate	High School Undergraduate	High School Graduate	College Undergraduate	College Graduate			
Teaching Methods	1.89	1.54	1.85	1.87	1.73	1.50	0.105	0.05	Not Significant
Feedback	3.42	3.31	3.00	3.07	3.33	4.00	0.316	0.05	Not Significant
Communication	1.58	1.43	1.50	1.53	1.53	1.50	0.909	0.05	Not Significant
Reading Resources	3.09	3.00	2.85	2.87	3.00	3.50	0.731	0.05	Not Significant

Table 25 presents the results of the test of significant difference in the teacher-related challenges encountered by the Grade 7 students in reading English when grouped according to parent's educational level.

The results showed that the value for teaching methods, feedback, communication, and reading resources is greater than the significance level of 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted at the 0.05 level of significance, thus, there is no significant difference in the teacher-related challenges in teaching methods, feedback, communication, and reading resources encountered by Grade 7 students when grouped by their parents' educational level. This implies that the students do not differ in the challenges encountered in teaching methods, feedback, communication, and reading resources when grouped by parents' educational level. It further indicates that students

with similar parents' educational level exhibit similar challenges in these areas. This finding is consistent with the study by Linek et al.(1997), who reported that parents' educational level had no significant effect on their perception of parent-teacher communication, implying that teacher-related factors such as instructional methods, feedback, communication style, and resource use are perceived similarly by students regardless of their parents' educational attainment.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the study shows that Grade 7 students faced several challenges in reading English, especially in reading comprehension and vocabulary skills, where many are at the frustration level. These difficulties affect their overall reading ability, even though many perform well in word recognition and reading speed. Among the learner-related challenges, comprehension and vocabulary are the most difficult for students. In terms of teacher-related challenges, feedback and reading resources are the main concerns. On the other hand, students do not find teaching methods and communication style to be big problems.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations were made.

1. Curriculum Planners should design a curriculum that actively emphasizes interactive and engaging reading strategies. Incorporating structured feedback and differentiated instruction to directly address the diverse reading needs of students, thereby supporting those at various proficiency levels.
2. DepEd officials should develop and enforce policies that integrate structured reading interventions. Special emphasis should be placed on improving reading comprehension and vocabulary within the curriculum, ensuring these components are prioritized at all grade levels.
3. Education Supervisors should conduct regular teacher training focused on effective feedback strategies and enhancing reading resources to support students' comprehension and vocabulary development.
4. School Administrators should take immediate actions is needed to provide sufficient and varied reading materials, alongside programs that rigorously focus on improving students' reading comprehension and vocabulary skills.
5. Teachers must implement targeted interventions, such as guided reading sessions and vocabulary-building activities, to support students in improving both their comprehension and reading speed. Additionally, teachers should adapt the intervention plan, Project C.L.A.R.I.Z, developed by the researcher, to ensure personalized support and targeted improvement in reading comprehension, vocabulary development, and reading speed for Grade 7 students.
6. Learners should take an active role in their reading development by engaging consistently in reading activities, practicing comprehension exercises, and actively

seeking constructive feedback from teachers. This proactive approach greatly enhances their vocabulary and overall reading proficiency.

7. Parents must foster an environment that prioritizes regular reading habits, providing ample opportunities for students to practice reading outside school hours.
8. The researcher should further explore effective reading strategies, focusing on techniques that specifically address learners' challenges in comprehension and vocabulary.
9. Future studies should explore innovative teaching strategies and intervention programs aimed at improving students' reading performance. Emphasis must be placed on developing approaches that enhance comprehension, vocabulary, and reading speed to support sustained academic progress.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles governing educational research. Prior to the conduct of the study, formal permission was secured from the Schools Division Superintendent of the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan through appropriate official channels. Coordination was also made with the school head of Lupigue Integrated School before the administration of the research instruments. The respondents were properly informed about the purpose and nature of the study, and their participation was voluntary. The researcher ensured compliance with the Data Privacy Act in handling the students' demographic information and questionnaire responses. Confidentiality and anonymity of the respondents were strictly observed, and all data gathered were used solely for academic and research purposes. No participant was forced or coerced to take part in the study, and respect for the rights, welfare, and dignity of all respondents was upheld throughout the research process. The data collected were analyzed, interpreted, and presented with honesty, accuracy, and integrity.

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